

TGA-MS

**Deliverable 3.3, SOPs for all Physicochemical Methods,
Annex I, page 171.**

NFA standard Operating Procedure (SOP)

Chemistry

TGA-MS-screening 308 min.

Responsible: NMS

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TGA-MS-screening 308 min.

Preparation of sample

Analysis on the TGA-MS is carried out in crucibles of alumina (Al_2O_3) with volume of 3.4 ml. The mass of the crucible and lid is weighed before pouring the chosen sample (either liquids or powders) into the crucible. This is to determine the mass of the chosen sample (see the table below: Safety and precaution).

Safety and precaution

Chemicals	Instuction for use	H/P sætninger	
Name of chemical.	Instruction from selling company or NFA instruction	List of Hazard and Precaution sentences	<ul style="list-style-type: none">Text of Hazard and Precaution sentences
Silica_std Silica_Al Silica_Silane Silica_anis_Std Silica_anis_Al DPP_nano DPP_non-nano DPP_coated* CuPhthalo_nano CuPhthalo_halogen Fe2O3_nano_A Fe2O3_nano_B ZnCdSeS ZnCdSeS-COOH ZnCuInS/ZnS ZnCuInS/ZnS-COOH_smaller ZnCuInS/ZnS-COOH_larger CNF-50-nm CNF-80-nm Cellulose nanocrystals Ag-NW1_long Ag-NW2_short NM-402 Mitsui7 NM-212		General precaution for all the materials Try not to create dust clouds Don't ingest Wear gloves Use eye protection Don't spill the liquid For the most hazardous of the materials use glove box.	

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CeO ₂ (pyrolytic) NM-220 NM-300K NM-200 NM-110			
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* MSDS (Material Safety Data Sheet) or NFA instruction (APBA)

Safety instructions

Use proper fume hood with the necessary ventilation and filtering. Be careful not to create dust or drop liquids from the samples and follow the material safety data sheet instructions.

Starting the TGA-MS-screening

1. Weighing the sample for the TGA-MS-screening

Weigh the appropriate amount of material between 2-60 mg in the crucible within a fume hood with the proper ventilation and filters.

2. Transfer the crucible to the TGA-MS

Transfer of the crucible is done with the lit on which is held down with a gloved hand so no overspill can occur during transfer. Then mount the crucible on the TGA weight and drive down the furnace.

3. Preparation of the TGA-MS for screening

- The MS Temperature setting is set at 300 °C on the internal system and for the two transfer lines. The SEM and the filament is turn on.
- Choose the method called **Screening_TGA-MS_800** where the gas flow rate are purge gas 1 ambient air O₂/N₂ at 40 ml/min. and the balance protective gas 2 N₂ is set at 40 ml/min. and last step of cooling 60 ml/min of N₂ . The heat rate is 2,5°C/min. heating to 800°C. Then make sure that the starting temperature is at correct temperature 30°C and tarring the TGA weight to 0.000 mg and then press start. Now the TGA-MS is running.

4. Ending of the TGA-MS-screening for sample waste and disposal

- Wait until the crucible has cooled to room temperature.
- Transfer the crucible to a fume hood and use the proper waste disposal procedure for the given material that was analyzed.

5. Cleaning of the crucible

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The cleaning of the crucible is first done in a sonicator for 60 min. in deionized water and then following an organic solvent. The water and the organic solvent are properly disposed of in the waste disposal bin for solvent and water with chemical or material contaminants. The crucible is further cleaned in a furnace at 500 °C for evaporation of left over solvent or water species.

Log for corrections

Date	Change to	Change from	Initials
30/09-2019	No change	No change	nms